

Checklist of Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) associated with Rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) Carcasses in Andaman and Nicobar Islands

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Abstract

Forensic entomology deals with the investigation of crime especially post-mortem interval (PMI) with the help of insects. The prime witnesses to crime are the blowflies of the insect order Diptera, family Calliphoridae whose life history patterns help forensic entomologists to solve homicidal cases. But during the process of carcass faunal succession, some insects like ants, beetles, spiders, moths, etc. also impact the rate of decomposition. Among these insects, ants affect the rate of decomposition by removing large masses of fly maggots from carcasses for food. Ants also work on the body of the carcass in different ways and thus knowledge of these accidental visitors and their impact on succession is a prerequisite for the legal experts working in this field. During the faunal succession of the rabbit carcasses used as the animal model in Port Blair, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, the impact of ants and their role on the rate of decomposition by removing the eggs and larvae of forensically important flies from the carcasses has been observed. Accordingly, the checklist of forensically important ants with their detailed role in rabbit carcasses is provided to prepare baseline data for forensic and medicolegal experts for further investigation and reference for research.

Key words: ants, Formicidae, decomposition, post-mortem interval, forensic entomology, Andaman and Nicobar Islands

Introduction

Forensic entomology is the branch of science that calculates the PMI with the help of forensically important insects like flies and beetles (Greenberg, 1991; Byrd & Tomberlin, 2019). These insects are used to identify forensically important evidence like location and time of crime commission, estimation of time since death, any movement of the carcass from the original crime scene, and creating a link between suspects and the crime scene (Cruz, 2016; Al-Qahtni et al., 2019; Amendt et al., 2011). But a dead body being an ephemeral resource attracts other insects like ants and spiders, which feed on dead bodies with different life stages (larvae) of blow flies and beetles (Greenberg, 1991; Byrd & Tomberlin, 2019). These insects are typically classified as accidental visitors, but in many cases, their presence is not accidental but holds forensic significance (Bharti & Singh, 2003). Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) are one of the most diverse groups on the planet (Hölldobler et al., 1990; Sleight, 2003). They belong to one of the largest families, Formicidae, within the order Hymenoptera and represent the third largest insect order after Coleoptera and Diptera (Taylor, 2023). In addition, ants can also attract other omnivorous or predatory insects through their activity on carcass (Gunn, 2019). 887 valid species and subspecies belonging to 109 genera have been listed from India (Bharti et al., 2016; AntWiki, 2025). Wherein, 125 species of ants have been recorded from A&N Islands, but their association with carcasses has not been studied (Mohanraj et al., 2010). There are some studies where ants are seen on a dead body and create different patterns of scratch or abrasion (Byard et al.,

2014; Eubanks et al., 2019). In A&N of India, ants are seen creating abnormal post-mortem bleeding. This bleeding has been first classified to understand and clarify the role of ants in case of investigation, especially in fresh cases (Kumar et al., 2023). Also, research was required to identify the kinds of ants and how they affect a dead body in order to connect this to the case investigation and uncover more forensically significant facts (Tarone & Sanford, 2017; Mashaly et al., 2019). Therefore, to fill this gap, a preliminary study has been conducted at the Indian Council of Agriculture & Research-Central Island Agriculture Research Institute (ICAR-CIARI), Port Blair, A&N Islands, India (**Fig. 1**), gathered information on the rate of decomposition and identified various ant species visited the carcasses and recorded their effect on decomposition. In the decomposition process, the role of ants is found important from the beginning of the process of decomposition till the end of the skeletonization process. The ants might be counted as accidental visitors but impact the decomposition process including the rate of decomposition by removing the eggs of flies and also larvae from the decomposition area (de Souza et al., 2020). This information is important forensically because this impacts the estimation of time since death which is areas specific and dependent on climate and soil also (Yadav et al., 2024; Anderson, 2019; Kumar et al., 2024). Accordingly, the study of ants including the manner of working on carcasses and their types is important. In this study, the manner of working and types of forensically important ants from A&N Islands, India have been described on rabbit carcasses seasonally to prepare a database for forensic investigation and future research. Therefore, the role of ants becomes scientifically important from an investigation point of view (Maciel et al., 2016; Al-Qahtni et al., 2019).

Materials and methods

The collection and identification of ants during the decomposition process is an important task in understanding the role of ants in the decomposition process. In this study, the carcasses of rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) were used as research animals for estimating the time since death and the decomposition rate (Matuszewski et al., 2011; Mapara et al., 2012; Khalil et al., 2023). The rabbits were preferred due to their size, availability, cost, and easy ethical clearance (Mapara et al., 2012). As the rate of decomposition is climate-dependent (Yadav et al., 2024), so it was needed to measure temperature, humidity, and data of rain during the experiments. Accordingly, the experiments were conducted during the rainy and summer seasons of the A&N Islands (no cold in the A&N Islands). The carcasses were placed on the ground and covered by a metal cage, size 2.0 x 1.5 x 1.5 ft, which was protected by a wooden frame (3 m³) to protect the carcasses from vertebrate carnivores (Tantawi et al., 1996; Mashaly, 2016).

The sides of the cage were also protected by metal gauze to stop predator reptiles from damaging the carcasses. The carcasses were kept on the ground like the natural conditions to see the effect of climatic conditions and insects like flies and ants. The experiments were started in the morning hour by sacrificing animals with cervical dislocation to avoid any external injury. The mean (mean \pm SD) weight of carcasses was recorded as 1.38 \pm 0.17 Kg (manual scale) with the age of 180 \pm 8 days as the weight is also a factor involved in the estimation of the rate of decomposition (Zongo et al., 2023). The temperature of the environment, carcasses, and soil were recorded four times up to a week, then 2 times up to 15 days with a glass thermometer. The humidity of the area was recorded two times a day by a dry and wet bulb hygrometer made "ZEAL". In addition, the data on abiotic factors such as environmental temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall was also obtained from the CIARI meteorological station for confirmation which is located approximately 500 meters from the experimental site at CIARI, Port Blair. During the experiments, with all precautions, the samples of ants along with other insects were collected in different stages with the help of a soft brush and tweezers, and preserved in glass tubes in absolute alcohol for identification (Bharti & Singh, 2003). The different ants were collected in different tubes at different stages of decomposition (Singh et al., 2020). The stages of decomposition described were noticed as fresh, bloating, decay, dry, and skeletal. The ants were collected during all stages of decomposition including skeletonization. Observations were carried out regarding their food preferences, time of visit, abundance, and diversity to evaluate their impact on the decomposition rate (**Fig. 2**).

The ants were also observed for their actions on carcasses like necrophagous, predators, and omnivorous. For identification of the ants, Bingham, 1903, and other relevant literature were used.

Results and discussion

In this study, a total of 3 experiments were performed during the study. The carcasses of the rabbits were placed in July 2022, September 2022 (rainy season) and December 2022 (summer season) [Table 1]. There are only two seasons in A&N Islands i.e., summer, and rainy seasons. The major difference is of humidity and rainfall during two seasons. During the rainy and dry seasons, the duration of decomposition of fresh, bloated, decayed, dry, and skeletal carcass was similar except for the bloating stage which was attained earlier in the dry season. It indicates the role of temperature in the early start of decomposition (Yadav et al., 2024). In addition to this, the role of humidity and rain also affects the decomposition rate (Benny & Sulaiman, 2023).

Table 1. Range of temperature, humidity, and rain: Environmental condition

S. No.	Duration	Environmental temperature (°C)			Average Relative Humidity (%)	Average Rainfall of duration (mm)
		Min. ± SD	Max. ± SD	Average		
1.	Rainy Season July 17-July 23, 2022	24.95±.85	29.8 ±1.4	27.31	90.71	8.8
2.	Rainy Season Sept 18- Sept 24, 2022	25.35 ± 2.65	30.9 ± 1.1	27.95	83.21	4.2
3.	Dry Season Dec. 25 – Dec.31, 2022	24.1 ± 2.1	30.65 ± .75	27.60	67.64	0

Figure 3. Environmental condition

A total of 100 ants belonging to seven genera were collected during the present study. A total of 7 species of 7 genera were identified, wherein 6 species were common for rainy and dry seasons. Only one species namely *Oecophylla smaragdina* was exclusively observed in the dry season. The maximum frequency of *Tapinoma melanocephalum* was seen in the dry stage of the carcass whereas *Camponotus compressus* was noticed during the fresh stage of the carcass. *Camponotus compressus* was observed within 15 minutes of the placement of carcass in the field. The details of ants found and activities during different stages of decomposition and their association are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. List of Ants species visiting rabbit carcasses during different stages of decomposition

S. No	Ant species	Stage of decay		
		Rainy seasons (July 2022)	Rainy seasons (September 2022)	Dry seasons (December 2022)
1.	<i>Camponotus compressus</i> (Fabricius, 1787) (Major)	Fresh stage- ants were observed biting the soft areas of carcass mouth and creating abrasion. Decay stage- observed removing fly larvae	Fresh stage- Observed biting the carcass genital area	Fresh & bloating stage- Observed biting the soft areas of carcass mouth and backside of the carcass
2.	<i>Tetramorium bicarinatum</i> (Nylander, 1846)	Decay stage- observed removing fly larvae	Decay stage- observed collecting larvae Dry state- under the carcass in large numbers	Decay stage- observed collecting larvae

3.	<i>Diacamma indicum</i> Santschi, 1920	Fresh stage- ants observed biting the soft areas of carcass mouth and creating abrasions. Decay stage- observed collecting larvae	Fresh stage- ants observed biting the soft areas Decay stage- observed collecting larvae Dry state- Observed gathering the remnants of the carcass	Fresh stage- ants observed biting the soft areas of carcass mouth Decay stage- observed collecting larvae
4.	<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Bloating stage- observed moving on the body of the carcass Decay stage- observed collecting larvae	Decay stage- collecting larvae from the carcass Dry state- observed collecting dead larvae or remnants of carcass	Decay stage- observed gathering larvae Dry state- observed collecting dead larvae and remnants of the carcass
5.	<i>Carebara affinis</i> (Jerdon, 1851)	Bloating stage- observed moving on the carcass collecting eggs of flies Decay stage- observed collecting larvae Skeleton stage- observed moving on the skeleton of the carcass	Bloating stage- observed moving on the carcass collecting eggs of flies Decay stage- observed collecting larvae Dry state- observed working on dried skin with bones	Decay stage- observed collecting larvae Dry state- Observed working on the mummified body of the carcass, some ants under the carcass (Al-Qurashi et al., 2024)
6.	<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Bloating stage- observed moving on the carcass collecting eggs of flies' Dry stage- under the carcass skeleton (layer of hair and skin)	Fresh stage- some ants observed with carcass collecting eggs Dry stage- under the carcass in large numbers feeding dead larvae	Fresh observed on the eyes of the carcass (Chen et al. 2014) Decay stage- ants were observed working on the body of the carcass Dry stage- on the remnants of carcass and under the carcass in large numbers feeding dead larvae
7.	<i>Oecophylla smaragdina</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Not observed	Not observed	Dry state- observed collecting larvae of flies, in mass

The ants were observed in large numbers during the summer season which could be attributed to dry conditions. During the entire process of faunal succession, ants were either seen biting the carcass or collecting eggs and larvae for food (Barton & Evans, 2017). The same has also been noticed in other studies. Moreover, ants' bites caused abrasions on the carcass which further attracted flies (**Fig. 4**) (Michele et al., 2016; Greenberg, 1991). The presence of ants was seen in all the stages and thus their role as forensically important insects could not be overlooked by forensic experts (Andrade-Silva, 2015; Bharti & Singh, 2003). In the case of humans, it is hardly imagined that the ants may be so aggressive in creating bleeding to make it any suspicious activity (Kumar et al., 2023). Pau

During the study, *Tetramorium bicarinatum* and *Tapinoma melanocephalum* were observed foraging in groups and collecting eggs and larvae from the carcasses whereas *Camponotus compressus* and *Diacamma indicum* being solitary feeders were observed collecting larvae (Barton & Evans, 2017). Their abundance on the carcass may impact and affect the rate of decomposition, which is similar to other studies (Mendonça et al., 2019; Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990) (Fig. 5).

There may be different environmental conditions in different areas and accordingly, various species of ants may be seen with a dead body as per their adaptation. In normal cases, scratches are the prominent signs on a dead body created by the ants but if it concerns with cause of death and time since death, there is a need for some more research work. But if there is bleeding created by the ants or other similar situations that complicate an investigation, the study of ants in that particular area becomes a necessity to know more relevant information about ants and their effects on a dead body. Due to the Ants' activity, the colonization of carcass feeders i.e. larvae can be delayed or eliminate other insects from the carcass, thereby slowing down the decomposition process (Wells & Greenberg, 1994; Campobasso et al., 2009; Lindgren et al., 2011). If the rate of decomposition is also being affected by the presence of ants, that may also be explored in different biting patterns created by ants.

Conclusions

Given this backdrop, information about local ants is required for forensic as well as medicolegal experts as ants create different patterns on a dead body that may create chaos and confusion in reporting the case. Since different ant species leave distinct bite patterns on the body, understanding their behaviour becomes crucial. Additionally, any internal impact with forensic significance demands further investigation. There is very little information about the microscopic ant bite marks, and no ants have been categorized according to the biting marks. Therefore, preliminary research becomes necessary to get the data on ant biting patterns that are seen with dead bodies in a particular area and also their impact on a dead body. In this study, a preliminary checklist of forensically relevant ants of the Port Blair area is provided, which will act as baseline data for future reference in investigation and research as the ants of A&N Islands are found different creating bleeding and confusion for investigating agencies. However, a detailed study regarding the identification of ants as per their biting pattern, the impact of ant bites on the rate of decomposition, and the role of ants in the investigation is required in this area.

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